

WHOLE CHILD APPROACH TO EDUCATION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE VI PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

Through a Holistic Approach, students help achieve self-determination and establish responsibility at the early stage focuses on the emotional, social and academic needs of the students by cultivating a supportive atmosphere that maximizes their academic and non-academic needs. This study used descriptive researcher-made questionnaire. Purposive sampling was used to determine the respondents of this study. They were the 78 Grade VI pupils of San Crispin Elementary School, San Pablo City who are officially enrolled for the academic year 2020-2021. Pearson's r Correlation Coefficient was used in this study. The results show that majority of the Grade VI students were 12 years old females, with parents who are graduates of high school and college, with the father being the only one working for the family who receives a low monthly income. Majority of the respondents were Roman Catholics, with Tagalog ethnicity. They also belong to a medium-size family, being the eldest of married parents who prioritized education against all other family expenses. The respondents perceived that the school strives to promote wellness as an expression of their support for physiological needs. The social needs of the respondents also show manifest appreciation to good relationship with their teachers and their family's involvement to school activities and the community. The respondents' proficient academic performance is an evidence of their holistic development. Furthermore, the three Dimensions of Wholistic Child Approach; Physiological, Social and Emotional Needs influence the respondents' academic performance. This study suggests to promote activities that enhances the different areas of development of the learners.

Keywords: teaching strategy, holistic approach, physiological needs, social needs, emotional needs